

LINK AND MATCH MANAGEMENT IN VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS CENTERS OF EXCELLENT (CoE) IN INCREASING THE COMPETENCE OF VOCATIONAL SCHOOL GRADUATES

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Abstract

The general objective is to describe and analyze Link and Match Management at Center of Excellence (CoE) Vocational Schools in Increasing Graduate Competency at Vocational High Schools. The research method used in this research is descriptive qualitative. Theoretical basis, Management Theory from G. R Terry and Link and match theory from Putranto. The results of the planning research revealed that the Link and Match Management of Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement of Vocational High School Graduates implemented by these two Vocational Schools made it more directional for teachers to carry out their planning in a directed, service-oriented manner unlike before, when students were going to do a comparative study they only Pay attention to the instructions from the filler material. The organization of these two Vocational Schools is in accordance with the curriculum for industrial needs. However, excellent service/character has not been optimally implemented at this Vocational High School, so that students carrying out the trip still follow conventional rules. Implementation, implementation of Link and Match Management in Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement for Vocational High School Graduates after being assigned to these two Vocational Schools, the attitude of students shows their discipline to apply parts of the Center of Excellence series in Competency Improvement for Vocational High School Graduates in education that has been conveyed through the subjects given by the teacher excellent service, so that changes in students are significant. Evaluation in particular students only get a warning for disciplinary action. Deficiencies and negative events during activities in the field are discussed between fellow teachers or with managerial parties. In general, based on the results of the research, it can generally be concluded to describe and analyze the Link and Match Management of Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement of Vocational High School Graduates in Subang Regency.

Keywords: Management, Link and Match, Increasing Graduate Competency

INTRODUCTION

Link and Match Management of Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement of Vocational High School Graduates at Al-multi Subang Vocational High School and Domas 1 Karawang Vocational High School can be viewed from 5 aspects, namely input, process, output, outcome, and impact. The management

input aspects of Link and Match have been fulfilled, but in terms of content quality, several improvements are needed, such as in the development of planning mapping instruments and the preparation of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the implementation of education services. Aspects of the Link and match process at the Center of Excellence are carried out through 5 stages that form the Link and Match Management cycle of SMK Centers of Excellence in Increasing Graduate Competency, namely standard setting, graduate mapping, quality compliance plan, implementation of quality compliance, quality evaluation/audit. The output aspect of SPMI implementation is the fulfillment of the expected goals related to the fulfillment of the 8 SNP (SKL, Content Standards, Process Standards, Assessment Standards, Educators and Education Personnel Standards, Facilities and Infrastructure Standards, Financing Standards and Management Standards) by school management and the functioning of the TPMPS organization. The outcome aspect of Link and Match Management at Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement for AI-multi and Domas 1 Vocational High School graduates is the improvement in the quality of the learning process and school management in accordance with SNP and producing graduates who are ready to work. Meanwhile, the aspect of Link and Match Management Impact at SMK Centers of Excellence in Increasing Graduate Competencies at AI-multi Subang Vocational School and Domas 1 Vocational School is an increase in the competence of graduates of learning outcomes in schools, the establishment of a PK culture in schools, the SNP is fulfilled, there is a continuous improvement in the quality of education, accreditation value increases each period and public trust increases.

RESEARCH METHODS

Link and Match Management Research at SMK Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement for SMK Graduates at SMK AI-Multi Subang and SMK Domas 1 Karawang in accordance with the main elements that must be found as stated in the problem formulation, research objectives and benefits, so this research uses a quantitative research method Quantitative is a process of finding knowledge that uses data in the form of numbers as a tool to analyze information about what you want to know. (Kasiram (2008:149).

RESEARCH RESULT

1. Planning

Planning a link and match management program for the Vocational High School Vocational High School education program with a dimension of Center of Excellence in order to increase competence and produce quality SMK graduates and with graduates of this vocational school graduates are ready to work in the industrial world, students through educational programs and academic programs. These two programs must refer to the four link and match management education programs at SMK PK, namely: planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating.

2. Organizing

Principal leadership organizers refer to collegial collectives. Leadership Colligial collective principals do not place supervisors as a central point but involve all school principals at the Center for Excellence Vocational Schools to jointly lead and advance the Vocational High School at the Center for Excellence Vocational High School. So that the decisions taken are not based on his personal opinion but must consider the opinions and suggestions of all school principals, teachers, supervisors and line stakeholders so that it makes it easier for him to make various strategic and technical decisions in all lines of vocational school education.

The collegial collective leadership of SMK PK PK principals can assist teachers, staff in determining and implementing links and matches, organizational leadership standards for SMK PK, leadership management, as well as the functions, authorities and duties of the leadership functions of SMK PK schools. This link and match management can be a direction for planning a SMK Center of Excellence which is oriented towards the vision, mission, quality service, goals and objectives of quality schools to produce the best graduates. All decisions in planning SMK PK link and match are carried out through meeting activities.

3. Execution

Prior to the implementation of the Internship, the management of the department made rules that had to be obeyed by students who were going to carry out the Internship including student absences, student rules, vehicle departure and order when they arrived at the location, with excellent service in which the link and match management of the central SMK was implemented excellence for students carrying out procedures that have been applied by the school's vocational subjects for field work practice in the world of work and applied.

4. Evaluation

Evaluation of link and match management in vocational high schools the center of excellence at SMK AI-multi Subang has the following objectives:

- a) Knowing the ability of students. Educational evaluation can find out the ability of students from daily exams, UTS, UAS and from the value of academic assignments and assignments.
- b) Measuring the growth and development of students. Evaluation can see the development of students while they are students at SMK AI-Multi Subang and SMK Domas 1 Kkarawang.
- c) Diagnosing learning difficulties of students. Evaluation can map students' learning difficulties in both written tests and oral tests.
- d) Knowing the results of teaching. Through evaluation, the results of teaching teachers can be assessed whether the material is conveyed properly or not. The material conveyed by the teacher is understood by students or not.

- e) Knowing the results of learning. Evaluation can find out the learning outcomes from the UTS and UAS results.
- f) Knowing the achievement of the curriculum. Learning evaluation can determine the achievement of subject competency standards with learning outcomes.
- g) Knowing changes in student behavior, learning evaluation can find out changes in student attitudes from those who are not yet disciplined to be disciplined.

Through these seven evaluation indicators it makes it easier for PK SMK schools in student achievement and link and match management at SMK and has the typical values of vocational high schools AI-multi subang and SMK Domas 1 Karawang, Subang district.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusion

a. General Conclusion

In general, based on the results of the research, it can be generally concluded that to describe and analyze the Link and Match Management of Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement of Vocational High School Graduates in Subang Regency, it has been going well.

b. Special Conclusion

Based on the general conclusions above, the specific conclusions of this study are as follows:

- 1) From a planning perspective, it is known that the Link and Match Management of Vocational High Schools is the Center of Excellence in Competency Improvement for Vocational High School Graduates implemented by these two Private Vocational High Schools (SMKS) to make it more directed for teachers to carry out their planning in a directed, service-oriented manner like never before, students when they are going to do a comparative study they only pay attention to the direction of the material filler.
- 2) From an organizational point of view, these two Private Vocational High Schools (SMKS) are in accordance with the curriculum needs of the industry, however, excellent service has not been optimally implemented in this SMK.
- 3) In terms of implementation, the application of Link and Match Management in Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement for Vocational High School Graduates after being established in these two Private Vocational High Schools (SMKS), the attitude of students shows their discipline to apply parts of the Center of Excellence series in Competency Improvement of Vocational High School Graduates of education that has been conveyed through the subjects given by excellent service teachers, so that changes in students are significant.

- 4) In terms of evaluation, in particular, students only receive a warning for disciplinary action. Deficiencies and negative events during activities in the field are discussed between fellow teachers or with managerial parties.
- 5) In terms of the problem, the influence of the times that are increasingly advanced, this increases the possibility for students to be negatively affected by Link and Match Management in Vocational High Schools Centers of Excellence in Competency Improvement for Vocational High School Graduates. Of course, this is also quite a tough challenge for teachers to educate coaches for the expected competency improvement of school vocational school graduates.
- 6) In terms of solutions, the control system and supervising new teachers in schools are not only carried out by teachers/staff, but schools form or enforce multilevel coaching, namely the coaching system is also carried out by a supervisory team that has been selected and deemed appropriate to provide examples and guiding and training in schools, apart from that the school also forms a kind of management arrangement chaired by the school principal, this management functions to supervise or coach students in the school itself, this is one of the EXCELLENTs possessed by SMKS in Subang.

2. Suggestion

- a. For managers of educational institutions to improve the competence of graduates of school education in order to provide excellent service to students for the realization of graduates who are competent and in line with national education goals.
- b. For best practices for school principals to be imitated, adapted and modified in implementing PK by implementing Link and Match management independently.
- c. For the principals of SMK AI-Multi Subang and SMK Domas 1 Karawang, Subang district in planning, organizing, activating and evaluating policies related to vocational high school graduates by considering the supporting and inhibiting factors of their implementation.
- d. For teachers and staff of SMK AI-multi Subang and SMK Domas 1 who are qualified according to the demands of the times.
- e. For education managers in general, in order to improve the quality of school graduates through the implementation of link and match management at SMK PK in increasing the competence of graduates in schools and ready to enter the world of work.
- f. For the author as a contribution of thought in the process of implementing the link and match implementation of the Center of Excellence in increasing the competency of educational graduates at SMKS SMK AI-multi Subang and SMK Domas 1.
- g. Further researchers are expected to be able to continue further research by developing existing data while formulating a more integrated study.

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